

Research Article

Development and Characterization of a Composite Material Based on the Mixture of Gypsum Plaster and Rice Husk Ash

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Abstract

The disposal of rice husk in landfills and open fields can be problematic and could affect the environment and human health due to its low bulk density. As such, this work concentrates on the usage of rice husk ash for the development and characterization of gypsum plaster and rice husk ash mixture as composite materials. The composite materials were categorized at 10 %, 20 %, 30 %, 40 % and 50 % weight of rice husk ash (RHA) fillers and the gypsum plaster or plaster of Paris (POP) was cast neat at 0 % RHA, which served as the control. Mechanical and thermal properties: tensile strength, compressive strength, flexural strength, Young's modulus and percentage elongation at fracture of the composites were experimentally determined using the Tokyo universal testing machine. The microstructures of the composites were studied with Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) and Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (EDX). It was deduced from the analysis that the developed epoxy-rice husk ash composite will be suitable for engineering and building applications that could be subjected to compression and thermal effects.

Keywords: Rice husk, bulk density, composite, gypsum, mechanical, thermal, universal, testing.

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Introduction

The production of new materials can change both the manufacturing process and the products of the material. Nowadays Engineers are faced with the task of developing new material that has light weight, low cost and good mechanical and thermal properties. Developing a composite material (a multiphase material that could be artificially developed), which has been a promising option to the task faced by the Engineers, requires a low density particulate material like rice husk ash (RHA) in a gypsum plaster matrix to form it. Rice husk ash is a by-product of combustion of rice husk from rice mills (Zemke and Woods, 2008). A number of possible uses of RHA includes: as absorbents for oils and chemicals, soil ameliorants, source of silicon, insulation powder in steel mills, cement production and block production. More specialized applications include the use of this material as a catalyst support (Chumee *et al.*, 2008). However, there are only limited applications of rice husk ash in composite production, which this work concentrate on how best to explore other additional engineering options.

The application of spectrum of low cost material reinforced matrix composites is growing rapidly in many engineering sectors. In developing composite materials, Scientists and Engineers have ingeniously combined different types of materials: metals, ceramics, polymers or their combinations in addition to defined binders (or matrix) in order to produce a new generation of extraordinary materials. Most composites have been developed in order to improve on the combination of mechanical and thermal characteristics: stiffness, toughness, ambient and high temperature strength (Callister Jr., 2001). One advantage of a composite is that the properties of the materials that were combined to develop it could be induced or incorporated within the molecules of the new material. This work present the application of plaster of Paris (POP) as matrix into RHA particles (a locally available inexpensive material) in order to develop a new composite material, which is expected to be used as thermal insulators and decorative interiors.

Rice husk as agricultural waste has been shown to be abundantly available in Nigeria, but despite its abundance the optimum utilization is still inadequate for the development of engineering material. Its disposal in landfills and open fields can be problematic and could affect the environment and human health due to its low bulk density. Therefore, there is need to develop more ways of reducing the amount of the waste in the environment. This study seeks to employ the advantage of the abundance of RHA by using it as filler in a POP matrix to determine its effect on the mechanical and thermal properties of the composites formed.

Incorporating RHA particles in A356.2 alloy using stir casting technique as carried out by Prashad and Krishna (2011) showed that the hardness and ultimate stress of the composite form increases with increased RHA content, which obviously decreased the density of the composite material. Ahmadi *et al.* (2007) found that replacement of cement with rice husk ash to about 20 % volume in the matrix will improve the mechanical properties of the concrete. They posited that using pozzolans like rice husk ash will reduce the utilization of cement and lower the cost of cement material and construction of buildings. However, according to Prashad and Krishna (2017), the partial replacement of ordinary Portland cement by up to 30 % of RHA had not impaired the mechanical behaviour of bamboo-pulp reinforced cement composites. They further iterated that use of a low carbon content RHA decreased porosity in the matrix and enhanced interfacial bonding of the composites. Since the deterioration of cellulose, cement composites is closely related to moisture movement and alkalinity, it is concluded that introduction of low-carbon RHA can lead to improved durability performance of a composites material developed from the RHA.

Materials and Method

Materials

A standard plaster of Paris was used as the matrix material and was supplied by De Paragon Chuks Ventures Nigeria LTD, Maiduguri. The material is a crystalline mineral of hydrated calcium sulphate and is fine hygroscopic white powder with a melting point of 163 °C, it has a density of 2.76 g/cm³ and a molecular mass of 290.3 g/mol (IPCS, n.d). The filler material that was used in the mixture was rice husk ash, which was produced from rice husk waste and was sourced from a local mill at a Central Market of Biu Area. The finely milled rice husk fillers

Figure 1: Typical mould for the sampling of thermal properties

were collected in large quantity and washed with water to remove impurities like sand or dust particles and pieces of rice that were in the husk. After washing, it was air dried at room temperature for 48 hours in order to remove the moisture content. The dried rice husk was burnt in a furnace at 550 °C for ~ 6 hours in order to produce the RHA that could certify the requirements for the present investigation. A sieved powder of 300 µm in size was then produced using the Civil Engineering Sieving Equipment at the Workshop, University of Maiduguri. Horse hair fibre obtained from Monday Market, Maiduguri was used as the reinforcement material. Horse hair fibre was chosen because of its reliability, availability and cost effectiveness.

Methods

Preparation of the Composite Mould

Smooth wooden board was constructed in the form of a rectangular mould and the dimension of the mould is 300 × 100 × 40 mm, as Figure 1 show. The surfaces were rubbed with a soapy mixture of groundnut oil to ensure easy removal of the composite material. To test for the thermal properties of the composite material, a cylindrical container was used.

Fabrication of the Composite Material

Manual mixing method and hand lay-up technique were used for the production of the composite material and were prepared into samples B, C, D, E and F using 10, 20, 30, 40

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and 50 % weight fraction of RHA, respectively. The measured weight of RHA and POP was mixed in a bowl until the mixture became uniform and then water was added and stirred for 5 minutes. The mixture was poured into the mould to a level half the volume of the mould, thereafter a measured mass fibre of about 300 mm length was arranged on it and the mould was then completely filled. The surface of the composite was smoothed using a hand trowel and then allowed to set for some minutes. Finally the composite materials were removed from the mould and were based on sample A - F shown in Table 1 and also at specified dimensions as in Table 2, which was in order to test for the mechanical and thermal properties of A - F. The % weight of the RHA filler and POP were calculated based on Equations 1 and 2 (Callister Jr., 2001):

$$V_F = 100 - V_M \tag{1}$$

$$V_C = V_F + V_M \tag{2}$$

Where,

V_C , V_F and V_M are the weight of the composite material, RHA and POP matrix, respectively.

Table 1: Typical composition of the composite materials

Sample	Weight of RHA filler, V_F (%)	Weight POP Matrix, V_M (%)
A	0	100
B	10	90
C	20	80
D	30	70
E	40	60
F	50	50

Table 2: Sample size for the testing of mechanical and thermal properties

S/N	Tests	Length (mm)	Breadth (mm)	Width (mm)
1	Thermal cond., k	-	3*	107**
2	Tensile strength	300	50	8
3	Compressive strength	100	50	8
4	Flexural strength	150	50	8

* thickness, ** diameter

Table 3: Testing for the mechanical and thermal Properties

S/N	Properties	Sample size (mm)	Equipment	Location
1	Tensile strength	70	¹ UTM	² SML ³ UAM
2	Compressible strength	70	⁴ TUTM	² SML ³ UAM
3	Fluxural strength	70	⁵ FTM	² SML ³ UAM
4	Thermal conductivity	Varied	⁶ STRS	² SML ³ UAM
5	Resistivity	Varied	⁶ STRS	² SML ³ UAM

¹Universal Testing Machine, ²Strength of Materials Laboratory, ³University of Agriculture, Makurdi, ⁴Tokyo Universal Testing Machine, ⁵Flexural Testing Machine ⁶Set of Three Retort Stand

Table 3 shows a brief description of where data was obtained and the equipment used in capturing the mechanical and thermal (further explained below) properties and were followed up by calculating some of the variables based on Equations 3 - 9 :

$$\text{Tensile strength, } F_t = \frac{\text{force}}{\text{area}} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Tensile stress, } \sigma = \frac{\text{load}}{\text{area}} = \frac{P}{A} \quad (4)$$

$$\varepsilon = \frac{\Delta l}{l} = \frac{l_f - l_0}{l_0} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Young's modulus, } E = \frac{\text{stress}}{\text{strain}} = \frac{\sigma}{\varepsilon} \quad (6)$$

Where:

ε = tensile strain, Δl = change in length, l = original length, l_f = final length, l_0 = initial length

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$$\text{Compressive strength, } F_c = \frac{\text{force}}{\text{area}} \quad (7)$$

$$\text{Flexural strength, } F_f = \frac{FL}{bd^2} \quad (8)$$

Where F = flexural force (kN), L = length (mm), B = breadth (mm), D = thickness (mm)

The Procedure used in Obtaining the Thermal Conductivity

The experimental procedures followed in the determining the thermal conductivity and resistivity of the specimen includes: setting up the three retort stands, heat source, steam boiler, mercury in glass thermometer, stop watch and Lee-Charlton's apparatus. The room temperature was taken before the steam boiler was filled with water to nearly half its volume and placed on a heat source (stove) and heated to produce steam that caused a rise in temperature of the brass disc (specific heat capacity 380 J/kg K) and the sample specimens until a stable state temperature T_1 and T_2 were obtained within the selected time interval. The specimens were removed and the brass disc heated directly by the steam chamber for about 10 - 15 minutes until the temperature was slightly above T_1 . The steam chamber was then removed and sample specimen placed back on the brass disc. The initial temperature was recorded at time zero with the drop in temperature also recorded in every sixty seconds until when no further changes in temperature seen. The thermal conductivity was calculated based on Equation 9 (Lienhard IV and Lienhard V, 2000).

$$Q = \frac{kA\Delta T}{L} \quad (9)$$

Where

Q = Heat transfer rate (Watts), k = thermal conductivity of the material (W/m K), A = surface area through which the heat flow (m^2), ΔT = the temperature difference between the hot and cold sides of the material (K) and L = thickness or length of the material (mm).

Results and Discussion

Scanning Electron Microscopy and Energy Dispersive X-Ray Spectroscopy Analysis

The microstructural investigation of the moulded composite samples as in Figure 2 (a and b), was done at the Advanced Laboratory of Chemical Engineering, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria. In this case, only the test sample containing 30 % of RHA was analysed. The microanalysis devices applied in carrying out the study are Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), model Phenom Prox, model no: MVE 016477830 Phenom World,

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Eindhoven, Holland and XRF: X-SUPREME800 by Oxford instruments. The Phenom Prox SEM consists of microscope column, specimen chamber, vacuum system, computer monitor and many other instrument controls. To generate the micrograph of the composite, a prepared test sample of the composite was loaded on the specimen chamber, which was clamped by a conductive double sided carbon tape to make it (specimen) conductive. The cathode and magnetic lenses in the SEM created and focused a beam of electrons on the specimen. The interactions between the particles of the specimen and the electron beam in turn, generated backscattered electron beam which were collected, amplified and displayed on the cathode ray tube. Then, the beam and the cathode ray tube were synchronously scanned to produce surface image of the composite samples shown on computer screen as in Figure 2.

(a) 70 % POP-30 % RHA magnified up to 500x

(b) 70 % POP and 30 % RHA magnified up to 1000x

Figure 2: Micrograph of the composite materials (sample A) by SEM, model Phenom Prox

The Energy Dispersive X-Rays (EDX) X-SUPREME 800 consists of an x-ray source, a lithium drifted silicon detector, an analyser and a monitor as its major components. It was connected to power source and subsequently turned on by pressing the start button. The x-rays (primary beam) were generated from the x-ray tube and focused at the sample's surface by passing through a filter which modifies the beam. The interactions between the primary beam and the atoms in the sample prompted the atoms to emit secondary x-rays which were collected by the detector. The analytical lithium drifted silicon detector converted the x-ray energy into voltage signals which were measured and passed onto the analyzer to generate a spectrum showing the x-ray intensity peaks versus their energy. The peak energy identify the elements, the intensity gives an indication of its amount in the x-rayed sample, while the analyser used the information to calculate the sample's elemental composition and their percentage concentration. Thus, the results analysed were displayed on the monitor: SEM EDX.

Table 4: Elemental compositions of Sample D

Element	Symbol	wt (%)
Sodium	Na	0.6914
Magnesium	Mg	3.7222
Aluminium	Al	0.4397
Silicon	Si	21.4787
Phosphorus	P	0.3737
Sulphur	S	15.5706
Chlorine	Cl	0.0577
Potassium	K	0.1211
Calcium	Ca	54.8046
Titanium	Ti	0.0098
Chromium	Cr	0.0000
Manganese	Mn	0.0311
Iron	Fe	0.0858
Zinc	Zn	2.2365
Strontium	Sr	0.3771

Scanning Electron Microscopy

The aim of the SEM analysis was to observe the interaction of RHA fillers in the POP matrix. Magnifications up to 500x and 1000x were used in order to specifically characterize the specimen. An observation of the composite with 30 % RHA in Figures 2 (a and b) showed that the surface of the composite was rough and the rice husk ash particles were fairly distributed in the matrix. The rice husk ash particles were interacting

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at the interface. There is however, lack of adequate bonding between the particles with the matrix.

Energy Dispersive X-Ray Fluorescence Spectroscopy

Table 4 shows the elemental composition of the 70 % POP, 30 % RHA composite material. It shows that the developed 70 % POP, 30% RHA composite contains: calcium, sulphur and Silicon as the major elements. The surface of this composite allowed more reactions between the epoxy matrix and rice husk ash particles which accounted for the higher elements in its microstructure.

Mechanical Properties

Table 5 shows the samples (A, B, C and D) of the percentage in the mixture of POP and RHA, the basis of the characterization of the mechanical properties. The Table shows that compressibility is controlled by increased in RHA as its increased increases both the compressive force and strength, which is similar to the Young Modulus. While Flexural is controlled by the increased in POP, as both the force and strength in Table 5 indicates increment with increased POP and decreased RHA. The only surprising and unexpected trend is the tensile action on the composite material, as neither the increased in POP or RHA controls it, but there are haphazard trend in the data shown, which future work will investigate.

Table 5: Composition of the Composite Material based on their Mechanical Properties

Sample	Percentage of Mixed Materials	C.F (kN)	F_c (MPa)	F.F (kN)	F_f (kPa)	F_t (kPa)	E (MPa)
A	100 % POP 0 % RHA	8.00	1.60	5.5	257.81	372.67	13.80
B	90 % POP 10 % RHA	9.00	1.80	4.5	210.94	379.33	6.13
C	80 % POP 20 % RHA	9.80	1.96	3.0	140.63	360.00	8.74
D	70 % POP 30 % RHA	10.60	2.12	2.3	107.81	366.00	5.15

C.F - compressive force, F.F - flexural force, F_c - compressive strength, F_f - flexural strength, F_t - tensile strength and E - Young's modulus

Figure 3: Effect of the samples (A - D shown in Table 5) composition with stress and strain

Figure 4: Influence of load on the composite material with extension for sample A - B

Figure 3 shows how the cast neat POP and the composites reacted to tensile forces. The tensile strengths of the composites with 20 % and 30 % volume of RHA are lower than

the pure POP while the highest tensile strength of 379 kPa was recorded at 10 % volume of RHA. This is because tensile strength is affected by volume fractions, degree of adhesion between the filler and the matrix, level of dispersion of the filler and matrix and surface related defects (Nnaji, 2012). Tensile strength can decrease with increasing filler content if the filler matrix adhesion is

Figure 5: Effects of RHA (Table 5) weight fractions on the tensile strength of the composites

Figure 6: Effects of RHA (Table 5) weight composition on the Young's modulus of composite

weak and this account for the reason why the tensile strength of 20 % and 30 % volume fraction of RHA are lower than the pure POP. The increase in rice husk ash content led to greater possibility of weak locations in the composites which caused easy de-bonding at the interface when tensile forces were applied. However the reasons for the higher tensile strength of the 10 % RHA could be because there were strong interfacial adhesions between lesser rice husk ash fillers and POP matrix or better stirring during the production process.

Figure 4 shows the Young's modulus of the composite at different weight percentages of RHA. It can be seen that the cast neat POP had the highest tensile modulus of 13.80 MPa. The addition of rice husk ash fillers caused loss of tensile modulus because the manual mixing method used in the composite preparation caused some rice husk ash fillers to be poorly dispersed and this poorly dispersed fillers formed agglomerates. These agglomerated fillers acted as stress concentration sites due to their porous nature and weakened the composite stiffness on tension. Figures 5 - 8 also support the discussion shown for Table 5, whereby the impacts of mechanical properties were influenced by the composition of the samples (A - D) composition.

Figure 7: Influence of RHA (Table 5) weight composition on the flexural strength of composites

Figure 8: Influence of RHA (Table 5) weight fraction on the developed composite materials

Figure 9: Effects of RHA (Table 5) composition on thermal conductivity of the composite mix

Effects of Thermal Properties on the Composite Mixture

The study shows from the calculations of the thermal properties of the different POP-RHA composite material in Figure 9 that the thermal properties of the different composite materials varied at different filler percentages. The lowest conductivity was obtained at POP 60 %, RHA 40 % which is 0.111 W/m K. This suggests that POP - RHA used in this ration is more suitable to use as ceiling or building material than POP in its pure form which has a conductivity of 0.184.6 W/m K.

Conclusion

This current work reveals that composite materials can be developed from the mixture of rice husk ash (RHA) and gypsum plaster or plaster of Paris (POP). It also shows that the sheer scale of hypothetical scientific porous structure of RHA, poor dispersion and poor interfacial adhesion (or bonding) between RHA and POP leads to a decreased in flexural strength and tensile strength with increased in the percentage of RHA fillers, which shows that RHA is not a good reinforcement material.

The only revealed remarkable reinforcing effect of RHA fillers was on compression, as the compressive strengths of the developed composites were higher than the cast neat POP. This implies that the POP - RHA developed composites could be used for engineering and building applications, especially in areas where light weight and resistance to compression are required.

Also, the analysis of the thermal properties showed that the developed composite materials have low thermal conductivity even with the differences in RHA percentages. The lowest thermal conductivity was obtained from the mixture of 60 % POP and 40 % RHA, which is shown to be 0.111 W/m K. This shows that the developed composites that were moulded in this ratio could be better applied as ceiling or building material than POP in its pure form. This lowness in thermal conductivity implies that the material can discharge heat away from it and so could be apply in places where heat requirement is low.

In essence, rice husk ash had been shown to be applicable as extender filler, as composite materials as good engineering properties were developed from it. Therefore, by adequately utilizing this waste product, cost and environmental pollution could be minimized and hence jobs opportunities are likely created.

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